

Review Analysis of Luxury Hotels in Manila Based on the Report of Online Travel Agencies using SERVQUAL Framework

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Abstract: Online reviews are essential in the travel and hotel businesses. Because there are various types of hotels, customers frequently read online hotel reviews before making a reservation. Consumers like to share their ideas and hunt for information online, and they find the content of online reviews more useful than suggestions from other online information sources. Online customer reviews are a vast and open source of information on how customers feel about the quality of a company's service, particularly in the hotel business, where it is useful to gauge hotel quality based on customer input. The capacity to distinguish between positive and negative reviews at luxury hotels according to SERVQUAL attributes of tangibility, reliability, empathy, responsiveness and assurance could help hotels identify problems and prioritize solutions and offer better services of the Luxury hotels. The outcomes of the study will assist hotel management in gaining a complete knowledge of client complaints regarding service difficulties and promoting service enhancements. Managers can determine the most effective customer retention approach by knowing the likelihood of customer complaints over time. This study was conducted to examine and analyze the content of positive and negative customer reviews from Booking.com, Expedia, and TripAdvisor in five-star hotels in Manila. SERVQUAL dimensions was used to classify both positive and negative reviews from the selected OTAs in five-star hotels in Manila. Findings revealed that the responsiveness dimension in the recreational services area received the highest number of customer reviews than any other service area of the hotels gathered from the selected OTAs of the study.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Luxury Hotels, Online Reviews, Online Travel Agencies, Review Analysis, SERVQUAL Framework.

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction is crucial for the functioning of any organization, business, or corporation on the market. Customers' encounter is essential in determining whether they would use the products or services shortly. Since the majority of businesses' primary source of revenue is the customers, for over three decades, the topic of consumer pleasure has fascinated scholars and academics (Noranee et al., 2021). Because the characteristics of the service industry differ from those of the tangible product industry, it is difficult to determine a hotel's actual condition before the customer has stayed there (Kim & Kim, 2022). One of the main reasons that using and reading customer reviews is becoming more popular, especially in the hotel business, is that the customer cannot see the service before using it. In the past, travelers mainly used advertising materials like catalogs, brochures, and TV and radio ads, but this was "controlled" by the hotels and their partners. Before making a reservation, 81 percent of people read hotel reviews. More than half read between 6 and 12 reviews on average, and 52 percent will not book a hotel without reviews (Prodanova, 2021).

Customers often read reviews of hotels online before making a reservation since there are different kinds of hotels (Sangpikul, 2019). Online reviews are critical in tourism and hotel industries (Sann et al., 2022). Consumers want to share

their opinions and look for information online (Kim & Kim, 2022) and find the content of online reviews more useful than suggestions from other online information sources. Online reviews from customers are a large and open source of information about how customers feel about the quality of a company's service, especially in the hotel industry (Ali et al., 2021), where it is helpful to assess hotel quality based on customer feedback (Hien et al., 2022).

Online travel agency sites display consumer ratings and enable individuals to obtain past evaluations of the property's overall service quality and the qualities of particular amenities (Mellinas et al., 2019). In parallel, hotel businesses utilize online evaluations and ratings to inform their marketing selections and safeguard their online reputation (Xie et al., 2016). Previous studies examined hotel industry customer e-complaints via TripAdvisor (e.g., Çelebi & Dalgiç, 2022; Dincer & Alrawadieh, 2017; Sangpikul, 2021a). TripAdvisor is an indispensable platform for travelers to voice their thoughts on travel and service quality and share their hotel experiences. In a 2019 Tripadvisor survey, 89 percent said it would alter their original hotel image due to poor reviews (Prodanova, 2021). Piramanayagam and Kumar (2020) analyzed the reviews of budget hotels in India on well-known travel websites like TripAdvisor and Booking.com. According to Expedia (2019), Expedia is among the most rapidly expanding online travel agencies around Asia, providing tourists with a wide variety of accommodations, entertainment, and travel services at low prices. Furthermore, Ho (2017) analyzed hotel reviews on Expedia to determine how hotel management attempts to manage relationships with dissatisfied customers.

Manila has been the capital of the Philippines for four centuries and is the country's industrial center and global port of entry (Salita, n.d.). The best hotels in Manila range from architecturally significant, historic 5-star hotels to ultra-luxurious, modern 5-star hotels dripping with grandeur, style, and luxury. The hotels in Manila offer a blend of the past and the present, reflecting the rich history of the city that can be experienced on tours of Manila (Go, n.d.).

Every aspect of the operation can make or break a business regarding the most rigorous standards for luxury hotels. True luxury is what lies beneath the flash and splendor of the exterior. The service distinguishes luxury hotels in Manila from any other global city. The well-trained men and women exemplify and adhere to the best accommodation standards in the world. Nevertheless, what makes their service so distinctive, renowned, and uplifting is the expression and implementation of traits based on fundamental Filipino values (I'M Hotel, n.d.). Even though the term luxury connotes exclusivity, the luxury hospitality business has gained favor among the general community, including the younger generation (Vale, 2021).

The existing research gaps in the study are the following:

1. What is the distinction between positive and negative reviews of the selected luxury hotels in Manila related to the following service quality dimensions:

1.1 Reliability;

1.2 Assurance;

1.3 Tangibility;

1.4 Empathy;

1.5 Responsiveness?

2. What ratings are provided by the guests of the selected luxury hotels using the rating scale (stars)?

3. Based on the reviews using the rating scale (stars) provided, how do hotel personnel respond to the reviews of the guests?

4. What are the implications of the findings of the study?

Given the current gaps, this study plotted the positive and negative feedback of Luxury Hotels in Manila into comparative tables according to SERVQUAL dimensions and specific areas in hotels per Online Travel Agencies for the overall analysis, as well as determined how the Luxury Hotels in Manila enhanced its service performance in each dimension. Also, it investigated the impact of online positive and negative reviews on the service quality of Luxury Hotels in Manila. Finally, offered a literature review of positive and negative reviews on selected online travel agencies utilizing SERVQUAL for luxury hotels. Due to the comparative significance of the feedback, the findings helped hotel management acquire a complete knowledge of client complaints regarding service difficulties and promote service enhancements. Understanding the possibility of customer dissatisfaction at a particular period enables managers to determine the most effective customer retention methods. This study will also help future travelers set service quality standards when choosing a luxury hotel, as it can improve its services after analyzing the data. This research is also beneficial to future researchers because it would

allow them to gather information that would be useful in their research and answer some of their questions. The researchers conducted the study during the academic year 2021 until 2022 at the Luxury Hotels in Manila, gathering both negative and positive reviews from 2021 until 2022 using renowned online travel agencies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A previous study utilized the three-factor theory to examine in what way the function of accommodation features as basic, exciting, and performance components vary based on hotel star reviews and diverse client segments. Also, determine if these parameters differ for local versus foreign visitors and hotels with different star ratings. Li et al. (2020) gathered 412,784 user-generated TripAdvisor reviews from various Chinese cities to examine the three-factor theory using hotel rating systems and a variety of consumer categories. This research demonstrates that customers' perceptions of hotel performance vary depending on their origin and user ratings of hotels under evaluation, hence mitigating the asymmetric effect of hotel attributes on guest fulfillment. However, three-factor theory is irrelevant to the research topic because it provides a robust theoretical framework for comprehending consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction by accounting for the asymmetric impact of hotel attributes on customers' evaluations of hotel performance (Albayrak & Caber, 2015; Füller & Matzler, 2008; Matzler & Renzl, 2007; Mikulic & Prebezac, 2012).

Another study investigated ratings of guests speaking in Chinese and English in TripAdvisor hotel review website to detect any possible discrepancies in rating patterns. Additionally, Sann & Lai (2020) study seeks to determine the service quality or factors that impact guest satisfaction. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that English- and Chinese-speaking guests have a tendency to show distinct online rating patterns for the hotel qualities of service, cleanliness, room, sleep quality, location, and value, which led to the development of a framework for the study. However, the developed framework did not align with the current research topic, as the study aimed to gain insight into disparities in the Chinese- and English-speaking guests' online rating behavior patterns while posting hotel evaluations on TripAdvisor.

One study aimed to help hoteliers address performance-related concerns by analyzing user-generated web reviews by finding service gaps in these critical factors. Lee et al. (2020) identified nine service quality factors as "sensory experience," "brand," "hotel class," "sleep," "location," "room," "service," "value," as well as "cleaning." Additionally, this research applies three comparative theories to investigate the offered research issues: the satisfaction theory (Oliver, 2010), the theory of emotions (Bagozzi et al., 1999), including the atmospheric theory (Baker et al., 1992). However, these theories were not relevant to the present research subject. The study's primary aims were to validate and identify the relevant elements affecting hotel customers' satisfaction using user-generated content (UGC). Also, to explain how business intelligence approaches may be used to assess these key elements that affect the satisfaction of hotel guests.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

- **Reliability:** the capability to execute the service correctly and provide the promised service to customers. (Sangpikul, 2021a).
- **Assurance:** the capability to gain the trust and confidence of customers (Sangpikul, 2021a).
- **Tangibility:** amenities, ambiance, facilities, and infrastructure (Sangpikul, 2021a).
- **Empathy:** the capability to comprehend consumers' needs (Sangpikul, 2021a).

- **Responsiveness:** the capability to support consumers and provide quick services (Sangpikul, 2021a).

Previous research comparing different frameworks prompted researchers to apply SERVQUAL Theory. Service quality evaluations are one method for obtaining customer perspectives on hotel services. According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), an analysis of the quality of service evaluates the gap between the quality dimensions of expectations and performance. It compares expectations and the perceived performance of a service (Lewis & Booms, 1983, as cited in Sangpikul, 2021a; Parasuraman et al., 1988; Lo et al., 2015). To assess the effectiveness of a service that meets client needs is its purpose (Lo et al., 2015; Memarzadeh & Chang, 2015).

The SERVQUAL model, a multidimensional tool in research to evaluate expectations as well as the perspectives of service of consumers, can measure service quality. The model has five elements (Parasuraman et al., 1988) which are reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responsiveness. Expectancy-disconfirmation paradigm is the basis of the SERVQUAL model (Oliver, 1981) to determine the difference between customer expectations and actual service delivery. (Lewis & Booms, 1983, as cited in Sangpikul, 2021a; Parasuraman et al., 1988). Positive disconfirmation occurs when execution outperforms expectations, according to Oliver (1981) and Parasuraman et al. (1988). Negative customer dissatisfaction occurs, meanwhile, when performance falls short of expectations.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

The relationship between study variables is shown in Figure 2. Positive and negative reviews on selected Online Travel Agencies will be categorized according to the following hotel areas: Food and Beverage Services, Facilities, Front Desk, Guest Room, and Recreational Services. These reviews will then be categorized and analyzed according to the SERVQUAL dimensions of reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responsiveness to generate recommendations for customer satisfaction in luxury hotels.

Numerous studies have been conducted to define service quality in terms of consumers' subjective views and to determine the key factors that impact what quality of service is. Peres et al. (2021) examined user-generated content (UGC) in the hotel industry in Florianópolis-SC, Brazil, with the aim of determining the standard of aspects as well as the polarity of sentiments based on online reviews. TripAdvisor provided the data for the study, and SERVQUAL was used to evaluate the positive and negative TripAdvisor reviews. According to the conclusions of the study, consumers scored "room," "location," "ambiance," "staff," "breakfast," "parking," "reservation," plus "cost-benefit" the most frequently. The criteria that receive the lowest scores are "Room," "Parking," but also "Reservation." Location, ambiance, service, breakfast, and cost-effectiveness garnered the most positive comments. By categorizing feedback from guests as positive or negative, using SERVQUAL, researchers make it possible for future researchers to replicate their findings.

Another similar study examined the quality of the service of the four five-star hotels throughout Goa. The objectives of the study include measuring service quality and analyzing components of service quality that have a significant impact on customer satisfaction. In addition, Gaunker & Gaonkar (2020) utilized the SERVQUAL model to offer a conceptual context for the data. The study's research findings revealed a discrepancy between the service quality that customers perceived and expected. In addition, three components of service quality are identified using exploratory factor analysis: service reliability, employee assurance, and physical facilities. Furthermore, the study suggests that addressing service quality factors influencing customer satisfaction is essential to standardize service levels and eliminate the gap. Lastly, to improve service quality and increase customer satisfaction, hotel management could utilize the results of the recent study as a guide to conduct the SERVQUAL study.

Another comparable study examined the impact of hotel appearances reflected in online forums (e.g., online travel agency websites) on potential customers' ratings of expected customer satisfaction and booking intentions and the interaction of appearances and operational values on these outcomes. According to the study, hotels with such a high appearance value are more likely to be booked. In addition, the study could offer better services regarding the SERVQUAL attributes of tangibility, reliability, and assurance. Furthermore, Kirillova & Chan (2018) observed no significant effects on responsiveness and empathy in their research. Considering the aesthetic appeal, the hotel's utilitarian value had little effect on the outcomes. In addition, their research suggests that applying SERVQUAL in the hospitality setting could offer various insights from the product experience, and literature and highlight the limits of a product's appearance impact in eliciting favorable service quality ratings. The similarity between the current study and the study of Kirillova and Chan (2018) would be determined by analyzing online travel agency reviews with SERVQUAL. The SERVQUAL model could be used to evaluate the reviews of each dimension to gain a deeper understanding of customer complaints.

In summary, numerous aspects of online customer reviews have been examined in different contexts, but examining positive and negative feedback of Luxury Hotels according to SERVQUAL dimensions and specific areas in the hotel has received minimal attention. Existing literature is insufficient for understanding the impact of online positive and negative reviews on the service quality of hotels. The ability to identify the distinction between positive and negative reviews at luxury hotels related to the service quality dimensions can assist hotels in identifying problems and establishing solution priorities. Consequently, the study's findings will assist hotel management in acquiring a full grasp of client complaints regarding service concerns and promoting service enhancements. Understanding the likelihood of customer complaints over a period of time enables managers to decide on the most effective customer retention strategies.

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology of research is a qualitative approach. This is the most appropriate method for this research, as it examines and analyzes the content of positive and negative customer reviews from Booking.com, Expedia, and TripAdvisor in five-star hotels in Manila. It also classifies both positive and negative reviews into SERVQUAL dimensions. The qualitative research method is a different anthropology fieldwork methodology that encourages participation in the field, experience, comprehension, and actual life to examine human social activities and social relationships (Ying, 2017, as cited in Ye & Yu, 2018). The qualitative research method permits the successful resolution of intentionally made errors, unintentional errors, and misconceptions of the examined participants, resulting in a superior study outcome (Ye & Yu, 2018).

Furthermore, the researchers utilized review analysis, which converts unstructured consumer and product ratings and reviews gathered from various channels into structured data. The data can then aid decision-making and improve the quality of developed goods and services (Wonderflow, 2022). Moreover, the following guidelines from Lertputtarak & Samokhin (2017) were modified and used to analyze customer reviews. The methodology for selecting comments for this study consisted of only three parts. [a] First, the researchers chose comments from 2021-2022 on selected online travel agency sites from each hotel's listing based on their review score, which ranged from lowest to highest. Second, only comments written in English were coded for this study. Third, the researchers carefully selected the reviews from Booking.com, Expedia, and TripAdvisor. According to the collected reviews, some were neither positive nor negative. Therefore, the researchers decided to include the neutral category. The researchers categorized the classified customer reviews into specific hotel areas using a five-factor framework to analyze the hotel service quality. This framework incorporates Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy. Following the classification of both positive and negative reviews through the SERVQUAL dimension, the researchers described the data in frequency and percentage using descriptive statistics. By identifying the frequency and percentage, the researchers will know which category and dimension will receive the most significant number of comments. Furthermore, the researchers created a comparative table for analysis.

To obtain information from Booking.com, Expedia, and TripAdvisor's review sections, the researchers ensured that the reviewers' identities as well as the company name of luxury hotels in Manila remained anonymous and that no harm was caused. As a result, the Data Privacy Act of 2012 will not be violated because the selected online travel agencies' reviews were made public. The researchers also employed norming to identify the classification of reviews as positive, negative, or neutral. Norming refers to the transformations required to convert raw data into valuable and interpretable information. A Norm is a parameter that determines the distribution of the construct of interest in the target population (Escobar, 2020). The researchers decided to include neutral as a classification of reviews because some guests provided neither positive nor negative responses. In addition, the researchers employed thematic analysis because secondary data was utilized. Thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis technique that entails perusing a data set (such as transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups) and identifying meaning patterns across the data to derive themes. Thematic analysis is an active process of reflexivity in which the researcher's subjective experience plays a central role in deriving meaning from data. The use of thematic analysis was widespread in psychology and other qualitative research methods (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

DESCRIPTIVE EVALUATIVE USING SECONDARY DATA

Accredited Luxury Hotels in Manila	Online Travel Agency	Total Number of Reviews	Total Number of Reviews per Hotel
Hotel A	Booking.com	16	104
	Expedia	0	
	TripAdvisor	88	
Hotel B	Booking.com	64	77
	Expedia	3	
	TripAdvisor	10	
Hotel C	Booking.com	11	18
	Expedia	1	
	TripAdvisor	6	
Hotel D	Booking.com	82	97
	Expedia	3	
	TripAdvisor	12	
TOTAL		296	296

Massive amounts of textual data were examined using a systematic coding and sorting method to analyze the themes and relationships of word usage, recurrence, as well as communication structures (Gbrich, 2007; Mayring, 2000; Stemler, 2000). In addition, descriptive statistics, specifically the frequency count summation were used to convey information about the data in terms of frequency and percentage, as it summarizes and organizes data set characteristics (Bhandari, 2020). The frequency count summation is the calculation of the number of occurrences of a characteristic. This calculation includes both absolute (number) and relative (percentage) totals (University of Guelph, 2015).

Besides that, descriptive evaluation was utilized as the researchers evaluated reviews. Finally, the location of the study was at De La Salle University- Dasmariñas.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4: Total Number of Reviews of Hotels per Online Travel Agency

Hotel	TripAdvisor	Expedia	Booking.com
Hotel A	88	0	16
Hotel B	10	3	64
Hotel C	6	1	11
Hotel D	12	3	82
TOTAL	116	7	173

Table 4 shows the total number of hotel reviews based on the study's selected travel agencies. The findings revealed that eighty-eight (88) and sixteen (16) reviews were found on TripAdvisor and Booking.com for Hotel A. Meanwhile, for Hotel B, ten (10) reviews were found on TripAdvisor, three (3) for Expedia, and sixty-four (64) for Booking.com.

Additionally, for Hotel C, eleven (11) reviews were found on Booking.com, six (6) on TripAdvisor, and only one (1) on Expedia. Lastly, Hotel D had 82 reviews on Booking.com, 12 on TripAdvisor, and only three on Expedia.

Table 5: Distribution of Reviews by Respondents from Hotel A

Areas/Dimensions	Food & Beverages	Facilities	Front Desk	Guest Room	Recreational Services
Reliability	15	30	18	24	11
Assurance	18	25	22	20	26
Tangibility	26	18	18	30	12
Empathy	35	20	20	18	18
Responsiveness	20	11	26	12	67
TOTAL	104	104	104	104	104

Table 5 shows the distribution of reviews by the respondents from Hotel A. The findings revealed a total of one hundred four (104) reviews from each area/dimension that would determine the food & beverages, facilities, front desk, guest room, and recreational services offered by Hotel A.

For instance, the findings also obtained positive and negative reviews from the hotel, wherein the customer stated that:

Key Informant #1: *"The executive suite was spacious for my husband and me. The view from our room was stunning. We were on the 16th floor, perfect for a sunset view. The bed and pillows were comfortable."* **That said, this may imply that the room had a generous size, offering enough room for comfort and movement during their stay.**

Key Informant #2: *"The hotel ambiance was clean and well-looked, wherein it had a perfect location. The staff were very helpful, especially when we couldn't find our car key, they let us stay in the room when we waited for our car key spare to arrive."* **This indicates that the hotel maintained a high level of cleanliness and took care of the overall appearance, creating a pleasant environment for the guests. Aside from that, this showcases the staff's willingness to assist guests in resolving unexpected issues and their accommodating nature, which can enhance the overall guest experience.**

Key Informant #3: *"The pastries were good (the ensaymada is still one of the best), but we won't recommend folks coming here to stay just for the lobby lounge experience,"* **This suggests that while the pastries were enjoyable, the overall experience at the lobby lounge may not have met the reviewer's expectations or provided a standout experience worth recommending.**

Key Informant #4: *"I know the staff is short, but they are amazing, they have worked so hard to maintain the high standard of the hotel. Very courteous and professional!"* **This may imply that the reviewer appreciates the staff's hard work and dedication in maintaining the high standard of the hotel, considering their behavior contributes to a positive guest experience and reflects well on the hotel's commitment to customer service.**

Key Informant #5: *“The food is served with grace and it is all delicious. It was a pleasant stay with very helpful staff and clean facilities.”* **This may imply that the presentation and service of the food are executed with care and attention to detail. Additionally, the hotel maintains a high standard of cleanliness and hygiene, which contributes to a comfortable and enjoyable stay for guests.**

For negative reviews, here is what the researchers had obtained in the online reviews that can be found on TripAdvisor and Booking.com:

Key Informant #6: *“Lousy breakfast with staff acting like they are forced to serve. Staff at the pool area disappears most of the time. The coffee lounge at the lobby and security need to treat everyone with equal respect and dignity.”* **This means that the quality, variety, or overall experience of the breakfast did not meet their expectations since there may have been instances where some guests were not treated in a fair or respectful manner, leading to dissatisfaction.**

Key Informant #7: *“I had breakfast for 2 mornings, same juices. Would be nice to add different drinks like buko juice or ice tea, with calamansi juice or show some Pinoy pride drink.”* **This may imply that there is a lack of variety in the beverage options, potentially resulting in a repetitive experience for guests; thus, the reviewer had a desire for more diverse and refreshing beverage choices that reflect local flavors or show a sense of "Pinoy pride" (pride in Filipino culture).**

Key Informant #8: *“The booking I paid for was already in total, but when I arrived, they said they made a mistake and wanted me to pay more. Their mistake is not supposed to be my problem, and they should honor the paid agreement. It would have been easy for them to follow through even when they charged much less because it's just a room. It was their mistake, but they made me feel they had the right to return their commitment even when you had paid in full.”* **This indicates that the payment for the accommodation was settled, and the expectation was that no additional charges would be required upon arrival. Aside from that, this may also imply that the payment for the accommodation was settled, and the expectation was that no additional charges would be required upon arrival. Lastly, the hotel's actions left the reviewer feeling frustrated and mistreated, as the hotel attempted to backtrack on their previous agreement.**

Key Informant #9: *“Staff are not very friendly or helpful. Only once did the doorman open the door for us in our 4-day stay. Only two staff members helped provide information or directions to places we needed to go.”* **This implies that the interactions with the staff were not pleasant or accommodating, and they may have been unresponsive or indifferent to the needs of the guests since most of the staff encountered during their stay did not offer adequate assistance or guidance when it came to providing information about the hotel's surroundings or helping them navigate their way to desired locations.**

Key Informant #10: *“The comfort room had a kind of strong smell of cigarette smoke. I had already requested a spray, but the smell was still there.”* **This suggests that the odor of smoke was present, likely indicating that previous guests had smoked in the room or close to it. With that, the reviewer requested the hotel staff to provide an air freshener or deodorizer to help eliminate or mask the odor.**

Table 6: Distribution of Reviews by Respondents from Hotel B

Areas/Dimensions	Food & Beverages	Facilities	Front Desk	Guest Room	Recreational Services
Reliability	12	18	14	18	15
Assurance	15	14	13	19	16
Tangibility	16	17	13	12	19
Empathy	15	12	16	16	18
Responsiveness	19	16	21	9	12
TOTAL	77	77	77	77	77

Table 6 shows the distribution of reviews by the respondents from the Hotel B that was gathered in TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com. Based on the findings, there were a total of seventy-seven (77) reviews from each area/dimension of the hotel. Furthermore, the findings also obtained positive and negative reviews from the hotel, wherein the customer stated that:

Key Informant #1: *“It was a great place. The staff was wonderful, professional, and friendly. The staff was very polite. The music at the lower level was very entertaining and of good quality and taste. Secondly, the breakfast selection is a delightful Great breakfast selection. Overall, the facilities are working, and it's nice and neat.”* **This may imply that the staff's polite behavior indicates high customer service. Thus, this also implies various choices, pleasing the reviewer's preferences and contributing to a positive dining experience. Lastly, the facilities were clean and had a well-maintained environment, according to the reviewer.**

Key Informant #2: *“The hotel's standout feature is its staff, all of whom were very friendly and accommodating Great place to stay in Makati since the rooms are spacious. It was also well located, within walking distance of Robinsons mall and a short ride from the National Museums, Intramuros, etc.”* **This positive review implies that positive interactions with the staff likely contributed to a pleasant and comfortable stay. Thus, Hotel B offers ample space for guests that could allow for a comfortable and relaxing stay. Lastly, this can enhance the overall experience in which guests feel more at ease during their stay.**

Key Informant #3: *“Old but with gold service, We stayed for a couple of nights just to relax and experience walking within dolomite sand (we are from Cebu, by the way) there was good scenery, including from our room view.”* **This implies that despite the hotel's age or appearance, the staff's level of service was exceptional, meeting or exceeding their expectations. In line with that, this also indicates that the hotel offered an opportunity for relaxation and provided access to the dolomite sand, likely in a scenic location.**

Key Informant #4: *“I must have used this hotel over five times this year, and the front desk check-in and check-out services have been very efficient. I mention Ms. MJ Decena, who has helped me on several occasions. Thank you for your unique way of caring for regular customers.”* **This statement implies that the hotel's front desk staff members are attentive, organized, and capable of handling the check-in and check-out processes smoothly, resulting in a seamless experience for the reviewer. Therefore, the hotel has been implementing specific strategies or practices to make their regular guests feel valued and well-taken care of.**

Key Informant #5: *“The guys cleaning our room are good as they constantly replenish our used stuff (sorry, I forgot to get their names as I am swamped every time they are cleaning). Still, the guy wearing a coat never missed knocking on our door every afternoon, asking if our room was already clean or if we needed anything; I think his name was Zyus. I never experienced that kind of service from my previous hotels. These are the Gold Within”* **This means that the cleaning staff is proactive in maintaining the cleanliness and tidiness of the room, knowing that these staff ensure the necessary items are regularly restocked— providing convenience to the customer experience of the guests. In addition, the service provided by the cleaning staff has given the experience of the guests a remarkable one.**

As per the negative reviews, below is the data that was obtained in the selected online travel agencies:

Key Informant #6: *“The only real issue is the housekeeping staff could be better. I had to call a couple of times to get the room made up on different days. Even after that, we had no new bath soap one day. Plus, I'm not too fond of the little bottles that are so non-eco-friendly.”* **The guest may have experienced some shortcomings or inconsistencies in the services provided by the housekeeping staff of Hotel B. Lastly, the guest expresses their dissatisfaction with the use of small bottles, which they perceive as non-eco-friendly.**

Key Informant #7: *“I had a bad encounter with the receptionist in club-Oasis named Karin. While we were signing in and going to the pool area with my family, she asked me how many people would use the pool with her high tone of voice and grumpy face, like we were criminals!”* **This suggests that Karin's (hotel staff) demeanor was unfriendly, unwelcoming, or disrespectful. The reviewer perceived these behaviors as inappropriate and unwarranted; thus, this indicates that Karin's tone and expression conveyed suspicion or hostility towards the reviewer and their family, creating an uncomfortable and unwarranted situation.**

Key Informant #8: *“Dinner in the Market Cafe is costly; if the breakfast is not free with the stay, that too is very expensive.”* **This suggests that the prices of the dishes or the overall dining experience are not perceived as providing good value for money. The reviewer may have expected more reasonable or affordable options for dinner; considering that the perceived expense may be in relation to the variety and quality of the breakfast offerings.**

Key Informant #9: *“The only negative thing is the low ceiling car park and the absence of a ramp from the car park to the elevator and from the elevator to the front desk - for ease in rolling luggage.”* **The guest points out that the absence of a ramp makes it challenging to maneuver luggage smoothly from the car park to the elevator and from the elevator to the front desk. This lack of accessibility can be seen as a drawback for guests who require assistance with their luggage or have mobility limitations.**

Key Informant #10: *“I can't believe they didn't find my clothes in the closet. I just remembered that I had to take it since the concierge returned twice because we had many luggage items. Someone took it or didn't give it to me because they initially said it wasn't there and kept their word. It could have been more enjoyable for a 5-star hotel.”* **The guest is surprised and unable to believe that the hotel staff did not find their clothes in the closet. Thus, the guest believes that the initial statement by the hotel staff claiming the clothes were not found was incorrect and that their word should have been kept. Lastly, the failure to locate the clothes and the perceived mishandling or lack of transparency in the process likely harmed the guest's overall satisfaction and perception of the hotel.**

Table 7: Distribution of Reviews by Respondents from Hotel C

Areas/Dimensions	Food & Beverages	Facilities	Front Desk	Guest Room	Recreational Services
Reliability	3	4	3	4	4
Assurance	4	3	3	4	4
Tangibility	3	4	3	4	4
Empathy	3	4	4	3	4
Responsiveness	5	2	4	3	4
TOTAL	18	18	18	18	18

Table 7 shows the overall total of reviews that was gathered from the selected OTAs of the study. Based on the findings, there were a total of eighteen (18) reviews from Hotel C. There are positives and negatives that were gathered from TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com. These are the evidence based on their statements below:

Key Informant #1: *“What I want to highlight is their top-notch & attentive in-person greeting and services, from the security and reception to housekeeping, swimming pool, and Pacific lounge. All workers were friendly, welcoming, and authentic.”* **This suggests that the hotel staff went above and beyond to provide exceptional customer service, meeting or exceeding the reviewer's expectations. Moreover, the workers in the mentioned departments exhibited friendly, welcoming, and authentic behavior. Their genuine hospitality and warmth contributed to a positive guest experience throughout the hotel.**

Key Informant #2: *“Despite not having a lounge, the pre-dinner buffet offered excellent value for enjoying small bites like a happy hour. For someone like me visiting from the US, the breakfast at this hotel is more of a full meal feast with sushi, salad, rice, local Filipino dishes, 20 different types of pastry, an omelet station, a noodle bar, etc.”* **This implies that the breakfast provided a generous selection of dishes and culinary delights, making it a significant meal of the day for the guest.**

Key Informant #3: *“The transport to the rest of Manila is relatively easy also. I recommend using Grab rather than taxis. This time I used the hotel's airport transfer and can highly recommend that, especially when you arrive! Transport from NAIA is a bit of a problem otherwise. The staff is warm and accommodating.”* **This implies that the hotel provides a reliable and efficient airport transfer service, which can be advantageous for guests, particularly when arriving at the airport. It offers a hassle-free and convenient transportation option.**

Key Informant #4: *“You get great views from the top floor restaurant and many of the rooms. I highly appreciate the pleasing staff and that I could see they truly tried their best to make sure guests were comfortable.”* **This indicates that the hotel staff made genuine efforts to go above and beyond in meeting guest needs and ensuring a comfortable stay, considering that these efforts likely included providing prompt and efficient service, addressing guest requests, and creating a hospitable environment.**

Key Informant #5: “Professionalism and friendliness of staff, down to the security guards. Was informed of the cell phone I forgot in the bathroom just w/in the hour after we left! Hence we were able to go back and retrieve it.” **This indicates that the staff consistently maintained a high level of professionalism in their interactions with guests and were friendly and approachable, creating a welcoming atmosphere; in comparison, the security guards were courteous, helpful, and attentive to guest needs, contributing to a safe and welcoming environment.**

As per the negative reviews, below is the data that was obtained from the selected travel agencies:

Key Informant #6: “The food included in the quarantine package was disappointing. I travel for work, and I’ve had quarantine stays in Philippine properties rated 3-star and 4-star, where their meal preparation was very generous, surpassing that of Hotel C.” **This means that the quality, variety, or overall dining experience did not meet their expectations, resulting in a less satisfactory dining experience during their quarantine stay. Thus, the guest highlighted that the meal preparation at those properties were very generous and exceeded their expectations, implying a higher quality or better selection of food options.**

Key Informant #7: “Given the relatively small range, I felt that the breakfast buffet was overpriced. Dishes ran out frequently. Much of the time, I had breakfast in the ground floor cafe (& more), which was much better value.” **This suggests that they feel the cost of the buffet does not align with the range or quality of the dishes offered, considering that the buffet lacks diversity or fails to consistently maintain a sufficient quantity of dishes, potentially leading to a less satisfactory experience for guests.**

Key Informant #8: “Online payment is a bit complicated; once you reserve at their website, you would still wait for an email from another service provider which would give you a code (which expires in 24 hours) to input at the third party's website to make your payment. I always get redirected to another website while attempting to make the payment, so I emailed their reservations team directly and paid via bank transfer.” **This suggests that the payment process may have encountered technical issues or was not seamlessly integrated, leading to a less-than-ideal user experience.**

Key Informant #9: “The traffic flow and parking. Considering Hotel C is a long-standing institution, one would expect the property to have ample entry and exit points and smooth traffic flow. They should have expected the number of people (and cars) arriving as they had prior knowledge of the bookings and events at the place.” **This suggests there may have been congestion or delays in accessing or exiting the hotel premises due to the volume of vehicles or insufficient infrastructure to handle the traffic; for instance, the guest expected that the hotel had adequate entry and exit points. With that, the guest anticipated a smoother flow of vehicles entering and leaving the premises.**

Key Informant #10: “The shower was too low. You can only shower comfortably if you sit in the bathtub. There was also no bidet. The window curtains need replacement as they cannot be opened widely to see the view. The window glass needs cleaning. Dirty carpets with stains. No bathrobes after swimming.” **The guest highlights various issues such as the low shower height, the absence of a bidet, the need to replace window curtains, the cleanliness of the window glass and carpets, and the lack of bathrobes after swimming, which contributed to the overall dissatisfaction of the hotel guest.**

Table 8: Distribution of Reviews by Respondents from the Hotel D

Areas/Dimensions	Food & Beverages	Facilities	Front Desk	Guest Room	Recreational Services
Reliability	20	15	16	25	25
Assurance	18	17	20	20	26
Tangibility	19	21	20	20	21
Empathy	20	25	20	18	18
Responsiveness	24	23	25	15	14
TOTAL	101	101	101	101	101

Table 8 shows the distribution of reviews by respondents from the Hotel D. Thus, based on the findings, there were a total of 101 reviews that were accumulated from TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com. Below were the reviews from made by the previous guests of Hotel D:

Key Informant #1: *"I spoke to Mr. Obediente and showed him the problem. We were moved to a much better room (409 on the new bldg) and very pleased. The Manila Hotel staff are wonderful people."* **This indicates that the hotel staff were responsive and proactive in resolving the problem. Additionally, this demonstrates the hotel recognized the issue and took appropriate action to ensure guest satisfaction by providing an upgraded accommodation. However, the guest exemplifies the hotel staff of the Hotel D as wonderful people.**

Key Informant #2: *"The location is excellent since Ermita is a lovely area near Rizal Park. We felt like a part of the hotel's history! Thus, with some exceptions, the staff were generally polite, pleasant, professional, friendly, and helpful! We enjoyed our first visit. Thanks to MJ and Ermine at the Front Desk for a smooth check-in and out!"* **This suggests that the hotel benefits from being situated in a charming area with convenient access to attractions and amenities, making it an ideal choice for guests who want to explore the surrounding area.**

Key Informant #3: *"The staff was terrific. I wish to thank the nurses in the hotel who took care of my back pain during my stay from June 30 to July 3. The nurses, Shye and Myrine, performed a fantastic job and professionally handled my low back pain. The medications prescribed to me by Nurse Shye performed very well, and I never had any back pain after that."* **The guest illustrates that the hotel staff was terrific, indicating that they provided exceptional service and care during the reviewer's stay. Aside from that, the nurses of the Manila Hotel had prescribed medications, provided the desired relief, and successfully managed the guest's symptoms.**

Key Informant #4: *"The rooms were not too expensive, and there were some good points. The view was spectacular over the city (although washing the windows would improve it) and there was a good bath, with bubbles which were nice after a long day."* **This indicates that the room offers panoramic views that the guest found impressive and visually appealing. However, they suggest that washing the windows would further improve the view.**

Key Informant #5: *"Breakfast menu? Delicious. Hotel D has an elaborate lobby and eye-catching displays. Thus, the Facilities are easy to access and user-friendly. Room is unique, antique looks, wooden carvings were nicely decorated and historical property on-time meal service."* **This indicates that the hotel has put effort into creating an attractive and visually appealing entrance area, contributing to a welcoming and impressive first impression for guests, considering that the room design incorporates historical elements and traditional aesthetics, creating a distinct and visually pleasing ambiance for guests.**

As per the negative reviews, below is the data that was obtained from the selected online travel agencies:

Key Informant #6: *"As a returning guest, I noticed a NO Dress Code when I ate at Cafe Ilang-Ilang during breakfast. I saw people coming in their pajamas, shower shoes, and slippers, and male guests coming in with a sleeveless shirt exposing their underarms. I related this issue to the head staff and informed them that Microtel (3 Star hotel close to MOA) has a dress code and wondered why Hotel D (5 Star) did not have any posted sign on their Cafe Ilang-Ilang entrance. They took notice and posted a DRESS CODE the following day. I hope that the hotel will maintain its high standard. Otherwise, guests will move to other better hotels in Manila."* **This indicates a deviation from the expected dress code standards for a hotel of The Hotel D's caliber since the guest expressed their concern regarding the mandatory dress code implemented by the hotel. Lastly, this concern is valid, considering that the hotel didn't regulate the guest's attire.**

Key Informant #7: *"The room smelled of cigarette smoke. The housekeeper even confirmed this with us when we asked him. We were appalled, especially as the wedding was the day after, and my sister was asthmatic. Clearly, the smoke detector wasn't working!!!"* **The guest notices a strong smell of cigarette smoke in the room. This indicates that the previous occupants or someone in the vicinity of the room may have been smoking, resulting in an unpleasant and undesirable odor. Thus, this review raises awareness about the effectiveness of the hotel's smoke detection and prevention systems.**

Key Informant #8: *"The Bride's room had a bedroom and a living room space. THE AIRCON WAS NOT WORKING EFFICIENTLY AS WELL!!! We were sweating as we hand-fanned ourselves!!! I asked for an electric fan, but they don't have one. One of the lifts was broken, so we had to use the other lift. After the wedding, we came back to the hotel. The second lift was also broken from the 4th to 3rd floors. Our room was on the 3rd floor, meaning we had to go up to the 4th floor and walk back down via stairs to reach the 3rd floor. We had to do this with all of our stuff from the wedding. IMAGINE*

THE STRUGGLE!! The reviewer expresses dissatisfaction with the air conditioning in the Bride's room, stating that it was not working efficiently. This suggests that the room did not provide the desired cooling and comfort, leading to discomfort and sweating. Hence, this also developed an inconvenience and required them to take an alternate route to reach their room, considering that there is a lack of functioning lifts inside the bride's room.

Key Informant #9: "I expected Hotel D to preserve the traditional Filipino style. But heck! the windows looked like there was 'anay'. It was creaking like in haunted house movies." The guest had expectations for Hotel D to preserve the traditional Filipino style. This suggests that they were looking forward to experiencing and appreciating the architectural and design elements that reflect Filipino culture and heritage.

Key Informant #10: "The Hotel D PUNISHED US for NOT booking DIRECTLY with them by refusing to let me book a taxi from the airport to the hotel! It felt like they avenged guests who DON'T make book rooms without seeing photos! (Me)The Executive Lounge was advertised as OPEN on BDC's app, but once I paid, the hotel sent me a message: "Sorry! Our Executive Lounge is CLOSED due to the Covid19 Pandemic." I called it the "Puñeta Suite!" "Switch and Bait?" Do you think your guests are that STUPID? BUYER BEWARE! The beautiful and smartly dressed Pinay at Front Desk could NOT recognize my CREDIT CARD! She goes: "Sorry. We DON'T accept Debit Cards!" This was even BEFORE she inserted it in the machine! She even asked me WHY I had to enter my four-digit PRIVATE PIN CODE! On our SECOND day, we went down for breakfast from our fourth-floor suite, and another Pinay asked us THREE times for our room number. "468? Are you SURE, Ma'am 468? Sir? 468 ?" Really?!" The reviewer feels that they were punished by the hotel for not booking directly with them, as they were refused the option to book a taxi from the airport to the hotel. This implies that the hotel may have withheld certain services or privileges as a result of the booking method chosen by the reviewer.

Table 9: Distribution of Reviews by Respondents from the Selected Hotels

Hotel	Very (1-2)	Poor (3-4)	Neutral (5-6)	Good (7-8)	Very Good (9-10)	%
Hotel A	7	9	13	20	58	40%
Hotel B	18	10	10	16	20	20%
Hotel C	1	2	2	4	9	10%
Hotel D	7	8	10	25	47	30%
TOTAL	33	29	35	65	134	100%

Based on the findings shown in Table 9, Hotel B received the highest number of "very poor" reviews, considering that there is a total of eighteen (18), respectively. Meanwhile, Hotel B also has the highest number of "poor" reviews that can be found on TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com since there are a total of ten (10) poor reviews. In addition, Hotel A has the highest number of "neutral" reviews, as there are thirteen (13) reviews.

Accordingly, Hotel D received the highest "good" reviews, with a total of twenty-five (25) reviews that were gathered in the selected OTAs. Lastly, Hotel A has the highest score in terms of "very good" reviews on TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com, with an overall score of fifty-eight (58), respectively.

Table 10: Summary of Total Reviews of Luxury Hotels per Areas/Dimensions

Areas/Dimensions	Food & Beverages	Facilities	Front Desk	Guest Room	Recreational Services	Total
Reliability	50	67	51	71	55	294
Assurance	55	59	58	63	72	307
Tangibility	64	60	54	66	56	300
Empathy	73	61	60	55	58	307
Responsiveness	68	52	76	39	97	332
Total	310	299	299	294	338	1540

Table 10 shows the summary of total reviews of luxury hotels per area/dimensions. The findings revealed that the responsiveness dimension received the highest number of reviews, considering that there is a total of three hundred and thirty-two (332), respectively. Meanwhile, the recreational services area also has the highest number of reviews that can be found on TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com since there are a total of three hundred and thirty-eight (338) reviews.

Table 11: Summary of Comment Categorization per Area/Dimension

Area/Dimensions	Acceptance and Appreciation	and Appreciation	Defense
Hotel A	<p>The reviews from the previous guests of Hotel A have acknowledged the hotel staff's efforts in providing excellent service and being professional despite being short-staffed. However, luxury hotels should also consider other ways to enhance the staff number to maintain service quality while preventing staff from overworking. In addition, Hotel A accepts praise for the quality of rooms, specifically the executive suite, as this contributed to a positive guest experience. Lastly, Hotel A should consider introducing Filipino food and beverages as this will showcase our cultural pride and enhance the guest's experience.</p>	<p>In terms of appreciation, the reviews expressed gratitude for Hotel A's hardworking staff; thus, the researchers believe that it is vital to recognize the efforts of the hotel staff, knowing that they are upholding the standards of the luxury hotel. Additionally, the reviews also appreciated the positive remarks about the cleanliness and ambiance of Hotel A. Lastly, the guests were approved of the quality of the food and beverages, as well as the service and facilities of Hotel A.</p>	<p>Hotel B addressed the concerns raised about the unequal treatment by some staff members, defending the hotel's principle of providing excellent service to all guests. Thus, Hotel B was also responding to the issues regarding the misunderstanding in the booking system (and also the extra charges made by one of the employees of Hotel A to their guest). However, this could be defended by being fair and taking accountability for the damages and inconveniences caused by Hotel A.</p>
Hotel B	<p>The guests recognized the high level of hospitality depicted by the staff. With that, it is essential to encourage and train staff to maintain friendly, professional behavior. For instance, the guests also acquired a positive review regarding the cleanliness and spaciousness of the luxury hotel's rooms; this implies that Hotel B was striving to maintain these standards across all of their rooms. In addition, Hotel B appreciates the positive comments on their hotel's location, wherein Hotel B persists in leveraging this advantage in providing information about nearby attractions to their guests.</p>	<p>The guests express gratitude for their appreciation towards their staff, explicitly acknowledging the individuals (or staff) for their dedicated hard work and exceptional customer service inside the hotel. For instance, the guest also appreciated the facility maintenance and working conditions of the facilities; this may indicate that Hotel B continues to upkeep its facilities to ensure that the guests are satisfied with their overall accommodation. Lastly, Hotel B was also impressive regarding their breakfast selection, as they were striving to maintain offering various food options and overall quality.</p>	<p>Hotel B has been addressing the inconsistencies and housekeeping services of Hotel B. With that, Hotel B needs to improve its service. Hotel B also responds to the concern raised about a particular staff's rude behavior, which will assure the guest that such behavior should not be allowed in the hotel's service standards. Additionally, Hotel B also responds to the criticism about the expensive hotel dining costs. Therefore, Hotel B clarifies its pricing policy and reflects on the meals' quality. Lastly, Hotel B also responded to the complaint about the lost clothes. Hotel B sincerely apologizes for the inconvenience caused and assures the guest of a thorough</p>

investigation into the matter to prevent such issues.

Hotel C

The reviews acknowledge the positive remarks about the staff's top-notch and attentive in-person greetings and services. The reviews appreciate the recognition of the staff's friendliness, professionalism, and authenticity. Additionally, the reviews acknowledge and appreciate the feedback regarding the delightful and extensive breakfast selection, considering that Hotel C aims to maintain the variety and quality of the breakfast offerings to cater to guests' will and ensure a satisfying dining experience. Lastly, The reviews also recognize the importance of reliable and efficient transportation options for guests, especially when arriving at the airport.

The reviews appreciate the recognition of the staff's exceptional service and efforts in ensuring guest comfort. This implies that Hotel C values the dedication and attentiveness of the staff members mentioned by name and will commend them for their outstanding service. Moreover, the reviews also express gratitude for the appreciation of the top-floor restaurant's views and the facilities' overall maintenance, and the hotel will continue to prioritize the upkeep of the premises to provide a pleasant and comfortable environment for guests.

Hotel C acknowledges the feedback about the disappointment with the quarantine package's food and recognizes the need to improve the quality and variety of the meals provided. Thus, the hotel will make necessary adjustments to ensure guests a more satisfactory dining experience during their quarantine stays. Consequently, Hotel C apologizes for any inconvenience caused by the complicated online payment process. Lastly, the hotel will review and streamline the process to ensure guests a smoother and more user-friendly payment experience.

Hotel D

Hotel D acknowledges the positive remarks about the staff's responsiveness and problem-solving abilities. This may indicate that the reviews appreciate the recognition of the staff's efforts in resolving issues and ensuring guest satisfaction. Thus, the positive reviews about Hotel D's location and being a part of the city's history helped the hotel to maintain its historical charm because this will offer the guests a unique hotel experience. Lastly, the reviews appreciated the nursing staff's exceptional care and professionalism. This may indicate that the hotel also values the well-being of its guests and continues to provide quality healthcare services.

The guests appreciated the recognition of the rooms' stunning views and the bath's enjoyment with bubbles. This may suggest that the hotel will continue to ensure that guests have the opportunity to appreciate the scenic views and enjoy the amenities provided. Thus, the reviews also appreciate the hotel's lobby and eye-catching displays.

Hotel D acknowledges the concern about the lack of a dress code at Cafe Ilang-Ilang during breakfast. Thus, Hotel D apologizes for any inconvenience caused by the cigarette smoke odor in the room. Therefore, the Hotel will review and enhance its smoke detection to ensure a smoke-free environment for the guests. Aside from that, Hotel D apologizes for the issues with the air conditioning in the Bride's room and the malfunctioning lifts. The hotel will immediately rectify these problems and ensure a comfortable stay for future guests. Furthermore, Hotel D regrets any inconvenience caused by the perceived booking, service, and communication difficulties. The hotel will review and improve its procedures to ensure a seamless booking experience and efficient service for all guests.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the responsiveness dimension in the recreational services area received the highest number of customer reviews than any other service area of the hotels gathered from the selected OTAs of the study. Some customer reviews of recreational services commended the attentiveness and courtesy of the staff, while others criticized the staff's customer communication. These customer reviews are concerned with responsiveness. Customer responsiveness can be improved by providing prompt services, demonstrating a greater willingness to assist customers, and providing accurate information regarding recreational facilities.

With that, the results in this study may imply that only Hotel A and Hotel D dominated the two (2) hotels in terms of their total number of reviews. Moreover, this may also imply that these luxury hotels have already developed a top-quality establishment— considering they consistently deliver exceptional experiences to their guests. Lastly, these hotels continuously improve their services to meet and exceed the guests' expectations.

Furthermore, the study also revealed that Hotel A has the highest score in terms of the overall positive reviews gathered from the selected OTAs of the study. Secondly, Hotel D also had the highest score in the total number of reviews. Meanwhile, Hotel B received the most negative reviews. For instance, Hotel D also had the highest number of reviews for being one of the most luxurious hotels that are located in Metro Manila. On the other hand, Hotel C had the lowest score in terms of its total reviews, which may imply that there were only a few guests who had experienced their overall accommodation.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, based on the analysis of customer reviews from TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com, it is evident that customer satisfaction plays a crucial role in the success of luxury hotels in Manila. The reviews provide valuable insights into various aspects of the hotels, including reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy, and responsiveness.

Thus, among the selected luxury hotels, Hotel A and Hotel D have received higher percentages of positive reviews, indicating higher customer satisfaction. These hotels have been praised for their attentive and friendly staff, well-maintained facilities, and enjoyable overall experiences. Positive interactions with hotel staff, comfortable and spacious rooms, and impressive amenities have contributed to the positive reviews.

On the other hand, Hotel B received more negative reviews, highlighting areas where improvements are needed. Issues such as poor service quality, cleanliness problems, and inadequate amenities were mentioned by dissatisfied guests. The hotel must address these concerns and implement measures to enhance its service standards, improve cleanliness, and provide a more satisfying guest experience. Accordingly, Hotel C had fewer reviews, but the majority were positive, indicating reasonable customer satisfaction. This implies that the hotel has successfully met guest expectations and provided a pleasant stay experience.

Furthermore, these selected luxury hotels in Manila should prioritize customer satisfaction by consistently delivering high-quality service, maintaining cleanliness and maintenance standards, and paying attention to guest feedback. Implementing staff training programs, regularly monitoring reviews on online platforms, and promptly addressing customer concerns can contribute to overall customer satisfaction. By enhancing service quality, maintaining facilities, and engaging with guests, luxury hotels in Manila can establish a positive reputation, attract more customers, and build long-term loyalty.

7. RECOMMENDATION

From the conclusion drawn above, the following points are strategic and tactical points that the selected luxury hotels may utilize, and future researchers can pursue further research:

- 1. Department of Tourism.** The DOT could create guidelines and requirements to enhance hotel service response. These could include required staff training programs that improve efficiency and customer service techniques, as well as minimum wait periods for food service and check-in/check-out.
- 2. Tourism Industry.** The industry should acknowledge the significance of service timeliness as a vital component of customer satisfaction. As a result, the hospitality industry should also host conferences, reports, and workshops that showcase best practices and ideas for enhancing these hotels' products and services.

3. Hotel Administration. The hotel administrations of the four (4) hotels (A, B, C, and D) in question and other hotels should make regular employee training and development investments emphasizing enhancing customer service responsiveness. In addition, since the front desk and food and beverage services were found to have the most significant influence on customer reviews, hotels must pay specific attention to them.

4. Hotel Personnel and Staff. The hotel personnel and staff should be more proficient in responding quickly and effectively to travelers' inquiries and concerns, particularly in front desk service. To handle these operations more effectively, these employees and staff should use other related technology tools, such as management software.

5. Hotel Guests. The hotel guests are encouraged to continue providing feedback, primarily through social media platforms or OTAs, as it acquires the hotel to identify areas for improvement and maintain standards within the hotel industry.

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